

Role of Drug Abuse on Academic Performance among Public Senior School Students in North Central Nigeria

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Abstract

The role of drug abuse on academic performance among public senior school students in north central Nigeria was investigated. The study is guided by one research question, and one hypothesis formulated and tested. Three research instruments, namely, Behavioural Problem Questionnaire (SBPQ), Mathematics Achievement Test (MAT) and English Language Achievement Test (ELAT) were for data collection. The SBPQ, MAT and ELAT were administered to 383 students drawn from 16 schools across North-Central States of Nigeria. The collected data were analyzed using Pearson product moment correlation to answer research question on the basis of the values of r (coefficient of correlation). Any correlation coefficient value below 0.50 was considered low while those above 0.50 was considered high. The formulated hypothesis was tested at 0.05 level of significance by comparing the p -value (probability values) of Pearson's product moment correlation obtained from SPSS application with the significance level at 0.05. Results show that there is no significant relationship between drug abuse and academic achievement of public senior secondary school students in north central Nigeria. Based on the findings, the study recommends that counseling services should be revived in schools for the purpose of providing therapy for learners involved in cases of drug abuse.

Keywords: Drug abuse, Academic performance, Students, Public, Senior secondary, School.

Introduction

Drug abuse appears very rampant in schools and in the society at large. It seems to be the source of one of a country's major health challenge as well as social problems. It has continued to be one of the most risk behaviour engaged and exhibited among secondary school students at present. The impact of these drugs been abused on daily bases by these secondary school students has remained a source of worry to parents, schools, the community, society stakeholders and even the government because of the attendant

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misbehaviours that usually follow it, may have negative effect on the society and educational achievement of the students. A drug is defined as any natural or artificial substance, other than food that by its chemical or physical nature alters structures in the living organism (Dorwick and Maline, 2007). Odejide (2000) defined drug abuse as drugs used in the face of legal prohibition or when a socially acceptable beverage is used excessively which can alter the mode of a person. This has also been observed by the researcher that some student's behavior is noticed to be altered, which makes them to carry out actions which are unwarranted by the environment. Abdullahi (2019) defined drug abuse as the use of drugs above the prescribed dosage and for the purpose other than for the original prescription. Although a lot of students use drugs as self-treatment of physical ailment which could result from ignorance but at the same time giving them pleasures to serve as a license in carrying out illegal activities such as bullying of schoolmates. The abuse of drugs may be detrimental to health and may cause harm to the individual and might make those involve in taking such harmful drugs wild. This might lead to a form of substance-related disorder and the rationale behind such actions is leading to poor adjustment of students psychologically, and poor achievements academically.

Young people who persistently abuse substances often experience an array of problems, including academic difficulties health-related problems, poor peer relationships and involvement with the juvenile justice system. Additionally, there are consequences for family members, the community, and the entire society like conflict between friends, family breakdown, violence, gangs, drug trafficking etc. Declining grades, absenteeism from school and other activities, and increased potential for dropping out of school are problems associated with adolescent substance abuse. Okoro (2019) had research finding that low level of commitment to education and higher truancy rates appear to be related to substance use among adolescents. Again, drugs abused effect the brain, this result in major decline in the functions carried out by the brain (Fayombo, 2000). Drugs affect the students concentration span, which is drastically reduced and boredom sets in much faster than for non-drug and substance abusers. The student will lose interest in school work including extra curriculum activities. Most of the psychoactive drugs affect the decision making process of the students, creative thinking and the development of the necessary life and social skills are stunted. They also interfere with the awareness of an individual's unique potential and interest thus affecting their career development (Okoro, 2009).

Cognitive and behavioural problems experienced by alcohol-and Drug-using youth may interfere with their academic performance and also present obstacles to learning for their classmate (Okoro, 2009). Drug abuse is associated with crime maintenance of an orderly and safe school atmosphere conducive to learning. It leads to destruction of school property and classroom disorder. Drug and substance abuse have far reaching ramifications, for instance, according to the survey by NACADA (2004) with a sample of 632 children, it was found out that 6% have ever engaged in sex while on drugs (7.3% for boys and 4.4% for 23 girls). The median age at sexual debut being estimated at 11 years. An assessment of the situation during the first sexual intercourse indicates that 30% had sex unwillingly. Furthermore, about 20% were given incentives to lure them in to sexual act, with a further 8% reporting having taken drugs before their first

sexual encounter. This early introduction into illicit sex goes a long way in impacting negatively on their self-esteem, exposing them to dangers of early pregnancy, contracting STIS and AIDS, declining academic performance and ultimately dropping out of school altogether (Okoro, 2019).

The worsening state of students' behavioural problems as well as the academic maladjustment in recent times has put them in a disadvantage disposition that makes it difficult for them to concentrate and learn better to attain high academic achievement. It is for this reason that this study seeks to examine the role of drug abuse on academic performance among public senior school students in north central Nigeria.

Research Question

The following research question guided the study

1. What is the relationship between drug abuse and academic achievement of public senior secondary school students in North Central, Nigeria?

Hypothesis

The following null hypothesis was formulated and was tested at 0.05 level of significance

1. There is no significant relationship between drug abuse and academic achievement public senior secondary school students in North Central, Nigeria.

Research Methods

This study adopted the correlation research design. Data were collected using a structured questionnaires titled Behavioural Problem Questionnaire (SBPQ), Mathematics Achievement Test (MAT) and English Language Achievement Test (ELAT). The SBPQ, MAT and ELAT were administered to 383 students drawn from 16 schools across North-Central States of Nigeria using simple random sampling technique of lucky dip. Furthermore, to answer the research question, the Pearson product moment correlation was used on the basis of the values of r (coefficient of correlation). Any correlation coefficient value below 0.50 was considered low while those above 0.50 was considered high. The hypothesis was however tested at 0.05 level of significance by comparing the p-value (probability values) of Pearson's product moment correlation obtained from SPSS application with the significance level at 0.05. Any hypothesis whose p-value is less than 0.05, is rejected or accepted when it is greater than 0.05.

Results and Discussion

Research Question 1: what is relationship between drug abuse and academic achievement of public senior secondary school students in North Central Zone, Nigeria?

Table 1. Calculated r-value of Pearson's Product Moment on the Level of Relationship between drug Abuse and Academic Achievement of Public Senior Secondary School students in North Central Zone, Nigeria

S/N	Variables	N	r	Remarks
1	Drug Abuse	383	0.054	Positively Low Relationship
2	Academic Achievement	383		

Table 1 shows the level of relationship between drug abuse and students; academic achievement of public senior secondary school students in North Central Zone, Nigeria. Results show that calculated r values is given as 0.054. Thus, value is below the benchmark value of 0.50. Hence, there is a positively low relationship between drug abuse and academic achievement of public senior secondary school students in North Central Zone, Nigeria.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between drug abuse and academic achievement of public senior secondary school students in North Central Zone, Nigeria?

Table 2. Calculated P-values of Pearson's Product Moment on the significance of Relationship between drug Abuse and Academic Achievement of Public Senior Secondary School students in North Central Zone, Nigeria

S/N	Variables	N	R	p-values	Decision	Remarks
1	Drug Abuse	383	0.054	0.290	Accept H ₀₁	Not Significant
2	Academic Achievement	383				

Table 2 shows the degree of relationship between drug abuse and students; academic achievement of public senior secondary school students in North Central Zone, Nigeria. Results show that p-value is given as 0.290. This value is above the 0.05 level of significance. Hence, hypothesis one is accepted indicating there is no significant relationship there is a no significant relationship between drug abuse and academic achievement of public senior secondary school students in North Central Zone, Nigeria.

Discussion of Results

From hypothesis one, it can be inferred that there is a no significant relationship between drug abuse and academic achievement of public senior secondary school students in North Central Zone, Nigeria. The finding is in contrast with findings from the study of Ndu et al. (2024) which indicated there was a significant impact of drug abuse on the academic performance of senior secondary students in Oshiri Development Centre, Onicha L.G.A of Ebonyi State. In addition, findings from the studies of Amadi and Akpelu (2018)

indicated significant influence of drug abuse on the academic performance of secondary school students in Emohua Local Government Area of Rivers State. Further findings from the research studies of Agbonghale and Okaka (2017) showed significant effect of drug abuse on the academic performance of students in Nigerian public universities. The study of Tuwei (2014) found there was significant influence of drug abuse on students' academic performance in public universities in Uasin Gishu County. However, in this study, the findings are in contrast since most of the students whom when sighted with the symptom even when given questionnaires to fill, would not tick the right answer in regards to what affects them and the researcher, guided by ethical standard, cannot force student to agree or even strongly agree to the options before them. Drugs affect the students concentration span, which will drastically reduce and boredom sets in much faster than for non-drug and substance abusers. The student will lose interest in school work including extra curriculum activities. Most of the psychoactive drugs affect the decision making process of the students, creative thinking and the development of the necessary life and social skills are stunted. They also interfere with the awareness of an individual's unique potential and interest thus affecting their career development (Okoro, 2009).

Conclusion

Having extensively discussed the relationship between drug abuse and academic performance of senior secondary school students, more needs to be done by both parents, school administrators, teachers, stakeholders, psychologists, government and the public on preventive measures that can keep our young adolescent students away from all forms of social vices, ill-relationships such as drug abusive. Therefore, school curriculum should be reviewed and modified in such a manner that will enable and meet the proper needs of secondary school students within the North Central States of Nigeria where the study was limited to. Based on the results of the present study, counseling services should be revived in schools for the purpose of providing therapy for learners involved in cases of drug abuse. Furthermore, even though findings from the study indicated there was no significant relationship between drug abuse and students' academic achievement, it is imperative for learners to be counseled on the need to avoid drug abuse as this may be detrimental to their future academic and career aspiration.

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